

Graphene Acid: A Potent Carbocatalyst for the Friedel–Crafts Arylation of Aldehydes with Indoles

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General Remarks

Chromatographic purification of products was accomplished using forced-flow chromatography on Merck[®] Kieselgel 60 70-230 mesh. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on aluminium-backed silica plates (0.2 mm, 60 F²⁵⁴). Visualization of the developed chromatogram was performed by fluorescence quenching using phosphomolybdic acid, anisaldehyde, or potassium permanganate stains. Melting points were determined on a Buchi[®] 530 hot-stage apparatus and were uncorrected. Mass spectra (ESI) were recorded on a Finningan[®] Surveyor MSQ LCMS spectrometer. HRMS spectra were recorded on a Bruker[®] Maxis Impact QTOF spectrometer. ¹H-NMR, ¹⁹F-NMR, and ¹³C-NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian[®] Mercury (200 MHz, 188 MHz, and 50 MHz, respectively) or on an Avance III HD Bruker 400 MHz (400 MHz, 376 MHz, and 100 MHz, respectively) and are internally referenced to residual solvent signals. Data for ¹H-NMR are reported as follows: chemical shift (δ ppm), integration, multiplicity (s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet, m = multiplet, br s = broad signal), coupling constant and assignment. Data for ¹⁹F-NMR are reported in terms of chemical shift (δ ppm) and are internally referenced to trifluoroacetic acid (188 MHz) or fluoroform (376 MHz). Data for ¹³C-NMR are reported in terms of chemical shift (δ ppm). Mass spectra and conversions of the reactions were recorded on a Shimadzu[®] GCMS-QP2010 Plus Gas Chromatograph Mass Spectrometer utilizing a MEGA[®] column (MEGA-5, F.T.: 0.25 μ m, I.D.: 0.25 mm, L.: 30 m, T_{max}: 350 °C, Column ID# 11475). Solid-state NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL spectrometer JNM-ECZ400R (working frequency: 399.8 MHz for ¹H, 376.3 MHz for ¹⁹F, and 100.5 MHz for ¹³C nuclei, respectively) equipped with a 3.2 mm MAS probe. All the spectra were measured at the MAS frequency of 18 kHz. To measure ¹⁹F-NMR spectra, the total suppression of spinning sidebands (TOSS) technique was used with a relaxation delay of 5 s. ¹⁹F-¹³C cross-polarization (CP)-MAS spectra were acquired under ¹⁹F irradiation offset of -184.14 ppm using contact time of 1 ms and relaxation delay of 5 s. ¹H-¹³C CP-MAS of GCN was recorded under ¹H irradiation offset of 2.49 ppm, relaxation delay of 6 s, and contact time of 8 ms. ¹H-¹³C CP-MAS of GA was recorded under ¹H irradiation offset of 5.88 ppm, relaxation delay of 5 s, and contact time of 7 ms. The recorded solid-

state NMR spectra were processed using JEOL Delta v6.1 software. Phase and baseline corrections were applied to the spectra.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was carried out with a Hitachi SU6600 instrument with accelerating voltage of 5 kV.

FT-IR spectra were recorded on an iS5 FTIR spectrometer (Thermo Nicolet) using the Smart Orbit ZnSe ATR accessory. Briefly, a droplet of an aqueous dispersion of the relevant material was placed on a ZnSe crystal and left to dry and form a film. Spectra were acquired by summing 32 scans recorded under a nitrogen gas flow through the ATR accessory. ATR and baseline corrections were applied to the collected spectra.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was carried out with a PHI VersaProbe II (Physical Electronics) spectrometer using an Al K α source (15 kV, 50 W). The obtained data were evaluated using the MultiPak (Ulvac - PHI, Inc.) software package. The charge correction of all the XPS spectra was done by positioning the maximum of the C 1s line to 284.8 eV.

Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectroscopy (ICP-MS) metal analysis was performed with a 7700ce instrument (Agilent). 1 mg of GA was added to a 5% nitric acid solution to form a final suspension of 50 mL. This suspension was sonicated for 3 h in order to unbind all metal ions from the graphene surface. Then, the suspension was filtered using a 100 nm filter to remove all graphene material from the solution. Subsequently, the filtrate was collected and measured by ICP-MS to determine the amount of metal ions that were bound to GA.

Synthesis and characterization of Cyanographene (GCN), Graphene Acid (GA), and Partially Fluorinated Graphene Acid (F-GA)

GCN and GA were synthesized according to the literature.¹ Briefly, fluorinated graphite (GrF) (240 mg, ~8.00 mmol) was placed in a round-bottom glass flask containing DMF (30 mL), and the mixture was stirred for 72 h and sonicated for 4 h under N₂ atmosphere. Then, NaCN (1.60 g, 32.00 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was heated at 130 °C for 24 h. Finally, G-CN was received by centrifugations and consecutive washing steps using acetone, ethanol, and water. Notably, a lower amount of NaCN (800 mg, 16.00 mmol), with respect to the above-mentioned one, was added for the synthesis of F-GCN towards the preparation of F-GA.

GA and F-GA were prepared after acidic hydrolysis of GCN or F-GCN, respectively. In detail, a suitable amount of HNO₃ (65%) was slowly added at room temperature under stirring to a suspension of GCN or F-GCN in H₂O (ratio of suspension: 1 mL of H₂O for 10 mg of material) in a round-bottom glass flask, until the final concentration of HNO₃ in the reaction mixture reached 20%. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was heated at 100 °C for 24 h. Graphene derivatives GA and F-GA were obtained after dialysis.

Figure S1. (A) Chemical procedure for the synthesis of GA, (B) FT-IR spectra of FG, G-CN, and GA, (C) XPS survey, and (C) C 1s XPS spectra of GA.

Figure S2. (A) Chemical structure of F-GA, (B) FT-IR, (C) XPS survey, and (D) C 1s XPS spectra of F-GA.

Table S1. Elemental composition of GA and F-GA, as obtained from the XPS analyses (integral values of HR-XPS spectra with subtracted Shirley background). The fluorine content of GA could not be quantified because of its low abundance in the GA. The value of the F atomic percentage of <1.0 at. % is shown, since the XPS detection limit is often quoted as 0.1-1.0 at. % and because it is evidently non-zero due to measurable ^{19}F NMR signals (Figure 1C).

	Atomic percentage [%]			
	C 1s (283 eV)	N 1s (400 eV)	O 1s (531 eV)	F 1s (686 eV)
GA	76.8	3.0	20.2	<1.0
F-GA	73.0	2.3	14.1	10.6

Table S2. Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) trace metal analysis of the carbocatalyst GA.

Element	Content ($\mu\text{g/g}$)
Mn	2.3
Fe	71.8
Cr	4.0
Cu	52.8
Ni	27.5
Co	Lower than the quantitation limit
Pd	Lower than the quantitation limit
Pt	Lower than the quantitation limit

Figure S3. Titration curve of 4 mL of GA dispersion in water (concentration 8 mg/mL). The equivalence point was determined as the maximum of the Gauss function fitted to the 1st derivative of the titration curve. The volume of 642 μL of the added 0.1M NaOH corresponds to the amount of 64.2 μmol of acid units per 32 mg of GA, making the total number of acid sites present in GA to be 2.006 $\mu\text{mol/mg}$.

Optimization of the Reaction Conditions for the Friedel-Crafts Arylation Between 3-Phenylpropanal (**1a**) and Indole (**2a**): Catalyst Loading

Table S3

Entry	Catalyst loading (mg)	Yield ^[a] (%)
1	1	35
2	2	44
3	5	70 (65)
4	10	70
5	20	70

[a] Yield determined by ¹H-NMR using an internal standard, yield of **4a** after isolation by column chromatography in parenthesis. The reaction was performed with 3-phenyl-propanal (**1a**) (13 mg, 0.10 mmol), indole (**2a**) (35 mg, 0.30 mmol), and catalyst **3** in water HPLC (3 mL) at 40 °C for 16 h.

Optimization of the Reaction Conditions for the Friedel-Crafts Arylation Between 3-Phenylpropanal (**1a**) and Indole (**2a**): Solvent Screening

Table S4

Entry	Solvent	Yield ^[a] (%)
1	MeCN	19
2	CH ₂ Cl ₂	48
3	CHCl ₃	12
4	EtOAc	20
5	DMSO	15
6	Toluene	15
7	Pet. Eth.	56
8	THF	16
9	Et ₂ O	63
10	MeOH	50
11	H ₂ O (HPLC)	70 (65)
12	Cyrene	-
13	2-Me-THF	23

[a] Yield determined by ¹H-NMR using an internal standard, yield of **4a** after isolation by column chromatography in parenthesis. The reaction was performed with 3-phenyl-propanal (**1a**) (13 mg, 0.10 mmol), indole (**2a**) (35 mg, 0.30 mmol), and catalyst **3** in solvent (3 mL) at 40 °C for 16 h.

Table S5

Entry	Solvent (mL)	Yield ^[a] (%)
1	1	44
2	2	59
3	3	70 (65)
4	4	62
5	5	55

[a] Yield determined by ¹H-NMR using an internal standard, yield of **4a** after isolation by column chromatography in parenthesis. The reaction was performed with 3-phenyl-propanal (**1a**) (13 mg, 0.10 mmol), indole (**2a**) (35 mg, 0.30 mmol), and catalyst **3** in water HPLC (1-5 mL) at 40 °C for 16 h.

Optimization of the Reaction Conditions for the Friedel-Crafts Arylation Between 3-Phenylpropanal (**1a**) and Indole (**2a**): Reaction Temperature

Table S6

Entry	Temperature (°C)	Yield ^[a] (%)
1	25	45
2	40	70 (65)
3	60	70 (68)

[a] Yield determined by ¹H-NMR using an internal standard, yield of **4a** after isolation by column chromatography in parenthesis. The reaction was performed with 3-phenyl-propanal (**1a**) (13 mg, 0.10 mmol), indole (**2a**) (35 mg, 0.30 mmol), and catalyst **3** in water HPLC (3 mL) at 25-60 °C for 16 h.

Optimization of the Reaction Conditions for the Friedel-Crafts Arylation Between 3-Phenylpropanal (**1a**) and Indole (**2a**): Indole Equivalents

Table S7

Entry	Indole (equiv.)	Yield ^[a] (%)
1	2.5	90 (88)
2	3	70 (65)
3	3.5	75
4	4	75

[a] Yield determined by ¹H-NMR using an internal standard, yield of **4a** after isolation by column chromatography in parenthesis. The reaction was performed with 3-phenyl-propanal (**1a**) (13 mg, 0.10 mmol), indole (**2a**), and catalyst **3** in water HPLC (3 mL) at 40 °C for 16 h.

Optimization of the Reaction Conditions for the Friedel-Crafts Arylation Between 3-Phenylpropanal (**1a**) and Indole (**2a**): Reaction

Time

Table S8

Entry	Time (h)	Yield ^[a] (%)
1	2	43
2	4	56
3	6	62
4	12	90
5	16	90 (88)
6	24	71
7	48	65

[a] Yield determined by ¹H-NMR using an internal standard, yield of **4a** after isolation by column chromatography in parenthesis. The reaction was performed with 3-phenyl-propanal (**1a**) (13 mg, 0.10 mmol), indole (**2a**) (29 mg, 0.25 mmol), and catalyst **3** in water HPLC (3 mL) at 40 °C in the range of time 2-48 h.

Optimization of the Reaction Conditions for the Friedel-Crafts Arylation Between 3-Phenylpropanal (**1a**) and Indole (**2a**): Ratio GA/H₂O

Table S9

Entry	G.A./H ₂ O (mg/mL)	Yield ^[a] (%)
1	1/0.6	69
2	2/1.2	91 (89)
3	5/3	90 (88)
4	10/6	94

[a] Yield determined by ¹H-NMR using an internal standard, yield of **4a** after isolation by column chromatography in parenthesis. The reaction was performed with 3-phenyl-propanal (**1a**) (13 mg, 0.10 mmol), indole (**2a**) (29 mg, 0.25 mmol), and catalyst **3** in water HPLC at 40 °C for 12 h.

Control Experiments to Study the Reaction Mechanism of the Friedel-Crafts Arylation

Table S10

Entry	Catalyst	Yield ^[a] (%)
1	No Catalyst	30
2	Graphene ^[b]	30
3	Benzoic acid	82
4	F-GA	63
5	GCN ^[c]	34
6	GA with NaHCO ₃	traces
7	GA	91

[a] Yield determined by ¹H-NMR using an internal standard, yield of **4a** after isolation by column chromatography in parenthesis. The reaction was performed with 3-phenyl-propanal (**1a**) (13 mg, 0.10 mmol), indole (**2a**) (29 mg, 0.25 mmol), and catalyst in water HPLC (1.2 mL) at 40 °C for 12 h.

[b] Graphene powder was purchased from Nanostructured & Amorphous Materials Inc.

[c] Cyanographene (GCN) is the precursor of GA (see reference 1 for its synthesis).

Synthesis of Starting Materials

1-Methyl-1*H*-indole (2b)²

To a stirring solution of indole (352 mg, 3.00 mmol) in dry THF (6 mL) at 0 °C, NaH (180 mg, 60% dispersion in mineral oil, 4.50 mmol) was added under an argon atmosphere. The heterogenous reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 15 min and at room temperature for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled at 0 °C, iodomethane (0.2 ml, 4.00 mmol) was added and allowed to warm at room temperature. After 30 min, the reaction mixture was cooled at 0 °C, quenched with saturated aq. NH₄Cl (5 mL) and extracted with diethyl ether (3 x 50 mL). The combined organic layers were washed with brine (1 x 50 ml), dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄, and concentrated in *vacuo*. The resulting oil was purified by flash chromatography (Pet. Ether/AcOEt 10:1); Green oil; 83% yield; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.68 (1H, d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.38 (1H, d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.28 (1H, t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.16 (1H, t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.10 (1H, d, *J* = 2.5 Hz, ArH), 6.54 (1H, d, *J* = 2.5 Hz, ArH), 3.84 (3H, s, NCH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 136.7, 128.7, 128.4, 121.4, 120.8, 119.2, 109.1, 100.9, 32.8; MS (ESI) *m/z* 154 [M+Na]⁺.

1-Benzyl-1*H*-indole (2c)²

Same procedure as above using benzyl bromide; Yellow solid, mp 39-40 °C; 82% yield; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.69 (1H, d, *J* = 7.8 Hz, ArH), 7.32-7.28 (4H, m, ArH), 7.17-7.11 (5H, m, ArH), 6.59 (1H, d, *J* = 2.3 Hz, ArH), 5.36 (2H, s, NCH₂);

^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 137.5, 136.3, 128.7, 128.6, 128.2, 127.6, 126.8, 121.7, 121.0, 119.5, 109.7, 101.7, 50.1; MS (ESI) m/z 230 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

1-Cyclopentyl-1*H*-indole (2d)²

Pd/C (560 mg, 20 mmol%), indole (234 mg, 2.00 mmol), HCO_2NH_4 (420 mg, 5.00 mmol) and distilled water (5 mL) were added into a Schlenk flask (25 mL) charged with a magnetic stir bar. After three cycles of evacuation/backfilling sequence with argon, cyclopentanone (530 μL , 6.00 mmol) were added. Then, the reaction mixture was stirred in a preheated oil bath at 100 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and then vacuum filtered through Celite and silica gel and washed with CH_2Cl_2 . The solvent was removed in vacuo and the crude mixture was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (Pet. Ether/AcOEt 10:1); Green oil; 95% yield; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.65 (1H, d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, ArH), 7.43 (1H, d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, ArH), 7.25-7.20 (2H, m, ArH), 7.15-7.09 (1H, m, ArH), 6.52 (1H, d, $J = 3.1$ Hz, ArH), 4.87- 4.79 (1H, m, NCH), 2.29-2.19 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.04-1.89 (4H, m, 2 x CH_2), 1.85-1.76 (2H, m, CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 136.1, 128.7, 124.5, 121.1, 120.9, 119.2, 109.8, 100.9, 56.9, 32.6, 24.1; MS (ESI) m/z 208 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

1-Butyl-1*H*-indole (2e)²

NaH (90 mg, 60% dispersion in mineral oil, 3.00 mmol) was added to indole (351 mg, 3.00 mmol) in dry DMSO (5 mL) under argon at room temperature and the reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h. Then, butyl iodide (772 mg, 4.20 mmol) was added and

the reaction mixture was stirred for 4.5 h. When the reaction was judged complete by TLC, water (50 mL) was added and the crude reaction mixture was extracted with chloroform (3 x 50 mL). The combined organic layers were dried with anhydrous Na₂SO₄, filtered and concentrated *in vacuo*. The resulting oil was purified by flash chromatography (Pet. Ether/AcOEt 20:1); Green oil; 51% yield; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.66 (1H, d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.38 (1H, d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.23 (1H, t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.15-7.09 (2H, m, ArH), 6.52 (1H, d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, ArH), 4.15 (2H, t, *J* = 7.1 Hz, NCH₂), 1.90-1.81 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.44-1.33 (2H, m, CH₂), 0.97 (3H, t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 136.0, 128.5, 127.8, 121.3, 120.9, 119.1, 109.4, 100.8, 46.1, 32.3, 20.2, 13.7; MS (ESI) *m/z* 196 [M+Na]⁺.

General Procedure for the Reaction between Aldehydes and Indoles

In a glass vial, containing graphene acid **3** (2 mg) in H₂O (HPLC, 1.2 mL), aldehyde (0.10 mmol) and indole (0.25 mmol) were added consecutively. The reaction mixture was stirred for 12 h at 40 °C. After reaction completion, the reaction mixture was extracted with EtOAc (3 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated *in vacuo*. The desired product was isolated after purification by column chromatography.

Photos showing the setup of the reaction (right panel) and the vessel containing GA before (down panel) and after (upper panel) the reaction.

3,3'-(3-Phenylpropane-1,1-diyl)bis(1H-indole) (4a)³

Brown solid; 89% yield; mp 156-158 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.88 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.59 (2H, d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, ArH), 7.38-7.27 (4H, m, ArH), 7.26-7.16 (5H, m, ArH), 7.07 (2H, t, *J* = 8.5 Hz, ArH), 7.03 (2H, s, ArH), 4.55 (1H, t, 8.1 Hz, CH), 2.80-2.74 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.64-2.54 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 142.6, 136.6, 128.5, 128.3, 127.1, 125.7, 121.8, 121.5, 120.1, 119.6, 119.1, 111.1, 37.4, 34.4, 33.5; MS (ESI) *m/z* 373 [M+Na]⁺.

Di-(1H-indol-3-yl)methane (4b)⁴

White solid; 90% yield; mp 160-162 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.93 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.65 (2H, d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.39 (2H, d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.22 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 7.12 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 6.97 (2H, s, ArH), 4.28 (2H, s, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 136.4, 127.6, 122.2, 121.9, 119.2, 119.2, 115.7, 111.0, 21.2; MS (ESI) *m/z* 269 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-(Butane-1,1-diyl)bis(1H-indole) (4c)⁵

Brown oil; 50% yield; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.90 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.63 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.36 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.18 (2H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 7.06 (2H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 7.03 (2H, s, ArH), 4.53 (1H, t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, CH), 2.28-2.19 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.52-1.42 (2H, m, CH_2), 0.99 (3H, t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 136.6, 127.2, 121.7, 121.3, 120.6, 119.7, 119.0, 111.0, 38.1, 33.7, 21.4, 14.2; MS (ESI) m/z 311 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3,3'-(Heptane)bis(1*H*-Indole) (4d)⁶

Brown oil; 94% yield; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.83 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.67 (2H, d, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 7.34 (2H, d, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 7.21 (2H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 7.11 (2H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 6.96 (2H, d, $J = 2.1$ Hz, ArH), 4.53 (1H, t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, CH), 2.32-2.21 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.53-1.38 (4H, m, 2 x CH_2), 1.36-1.26 (4H, m, 2 x CH_2), 0.93 (3H, t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 136.5, 127.2, 121.6, 121.4, 120.5, 119.6, 118.9, 111.0, 35.9, 34.0, 31.8, 29.4, 28.3, 22.7, 14.1; MS (ESI) m/z 353 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3,3'-(Dodecane-1,1-diyl)bis(1*H*-indole) (4e)⁷

Brown oil; 85% yield; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.88 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.64 (2H, d, $J = 7.4$ Hz, ArH), 7.35 (2H, d, $J = 7.4$ Hz, ArH), 7.18 (2H, t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, ArH), 7.07 (2H, t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, ArH), 7.01 (2H, s, ArH), 4.51 (1H, t, $J = 6.9$ Hz, CH), 2.30-2.18 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.36-1.21 (18H, m, 9 x CH_2), 0.96-0.88 (3H, m, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 136.6, 127.2, 121.7, 121.3, 120.6, 119.7, 119.0, 111.0, 35.9, 34.0, 31.9, 29.8, 29.7, 29.6, 29.3, 28.3, 22.7, 14.1; MS (ESI) m/z 423 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3,3'-(Octadecane-1,1-diyl)bis(1H-indole) (4f)

Brown oil; 50% yield; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.92 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.62 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.36 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.17 (2H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 7.06 (2H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 7.03 (2H, s, ArH), 4.50 (1H, t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, CH), 2.27-2.20 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.64-1.57 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.32-1.22 (28H, m, 14 x CH_2), 0.91 (3H, t, $J = 6.6$ Hz, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 136.6, 127.2, 121.7, 121.3, 120.6, 119.7, 119.0, 111.0, 35.8, 34.0, 31.9, 29.8, 29.7, 29.6, 29.5, 29.4, 28.3, 22.7, 14.1; HRMS exact mass calculated for $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ ($\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{48}\text{N}_2\text{Na}^+$) requires m/z 507.3710, found m/z 507.3716.

3,3'-(3-Methylbutane-1,1-diyl)bis(1H-indole) (4g)⁸

Red oil; 77% yield ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.75-7.69 (4H, m, 2 x NH and ArH), 7.33 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.24 (2H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 7.15 (2H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 6.93 (2H, s, ArH), 4.68 (1H, t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, CH), 2.18 (2H, t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, CH_2), 1.78-1.66 (1H, m, CH), 1.08 (6H, d, $J = 6.6$ Hz, 2 x CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 136.5, 127.0, 121.7, 121.4, 120.4, 119.5, 119.0, 111.1, 45.2, 31.6, 25.9, 22.8; MS (ESI) m/z 325 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3,3'-((Cyclohexane)methylene)bis(1H-Indole) (4h)⁹

Brown oil; 56% yield; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.90 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.69 (2H, d, $J = 7.9$ Hz, ArH), 7.33 (2H, d, $J = 7.9$ Hz, ArH), 7.16 (2H, t, $J = 7.9$ Hz, ArH), 7.11 (2H, d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, ArH), 7.08 (2H, t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, ArH), 4.31 (1H, d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, CH), 2.34-2.20 (1H, m, CH), 1.87 (2H, d, $J = 12.6$ Hz, 2 x CHH), 1.76-1.62 (4H, m, 4 x CHH), 1.24-1.04 (4H, m, 4 x CHH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 136.3, 127.8, 121.6, 121.5, 119.7, 119.7, 119.0, 110.9, 42.9, 40.1, 32.4, 26.7, 26.7; MS (ESI) m/z 351 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3,3'-((Phenylmethylene)bis(1H-indole) (4i)³

Red foam; 69% yield; mp 140-142 °C; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.77 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.45 (2H, d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, ArH), 7.40 (2H, d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, ArH), 7.37-7.30 (4H, m, ArH), 7.28 (1H, d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, ArH), 7.23 (2H, t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, ArH), 7.07 (2H, t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, ArH), 6.62 (2H, d, $J = 1.7$ Hz, ArH), 5.94 (1H, s, CH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz,

CDCl₃) δ : 144.0, 136.6, 128.7, 128.2, 127.0, 126.1, 123.6, 121.9, 119.9, 119.6, 119.2, 111.0, 40.2; MS (ESI) m/z 345 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-((4-Bromophenyl)methylene)bis(1*H*-indole) (4j)¹⁰

Red foam; 80% yield; mp 112-114 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.89 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.44-7.40 (4H, m, ArH), 7.36 (2H, d, J = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.24 (4H, d, J = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.07 (2H, t, J = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 6.60 (2H, s, ArH), 5.88 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 143.1, 136.6, 131.2, 130.4, 126.8, 123.6, 122.0, 119.8, 119.7, 119.3, 118.9, 111.1, 39.6; MS (ESI) m/z 425 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-((4-Chlorophenyl)methylene)bis(1*H*-indole) (4k)³

Orange foam; 72% yield; mp 77-79 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 7.70 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.47 (2H, d, J = 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.35 (2H, d, J = 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.32 (4H, s, ArH), 7.30-7.25 (2H, m, ArH), 7.15-7.10 (2H, m, ArH), 6.56 (2H, dd, J = 2.4 and 0.8 Hz, ArH), 5.93 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 142.5, 136.5, 131.7, 130.0, 128.3, 126.8, 123.6, 122.0, 119.7, 119.3, 118.9, 111.1, 39.5; MS (ESI) m/z 379 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-((4-Ethynylphenyl)methylene)bis(1*H*-indole) (4l)¹¹

Brown solid; 70% yield; mp 208-210 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 8.04 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.57 (2H, d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.47 (2H, d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.40 (2H, d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.36 (2H, d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.23 (2H, t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.06 (2H, t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 6.66 (2H, d, *J* = 2.2 Hz, ArH), 5.96 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 149.8, 136.7, 132.1, 129.5, 126.7, 123.6, 122.2, 119.5, 119.2, 119.1, 118.1, 111.2, 109.9, 40.3; MS (ESI) *m/z* 370 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-((4-(Trifluoromethyl)phenyl)methylene)bis(1*H*-indole) (4m)³

Brown foam; 67% yield; mp 67-69 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.79 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.60 (2H, d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.51 (2H, d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.46 (2H, d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.38 (2H, d, *J* = 8.1 Hz, ArH), 7.31-7.26 (2H, m, ArH), 7.16-7.10 (2H, m, ArH), 6.61 (2H, dd, *J* = 2.4 and 0.8 Hz, ArH), 6.01 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 148.1, 136.6, 129.1, 128.5 (q, *J* = 32.0 Hz), 126.9, 125.3, 125.3 (q, *J* = 3.7 Hz), 124.5 (q, *J* = 272.0 Hz), 123.8, 122.3, 119.8, 119.5, 118.8, 111.3, 40.2; ¹⁹F NMR: (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 62.1; MS (ESI) *m/z* 413 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-(*p*-Tolylmethylene)bis(1*H*-indole) (4n)¹²

Brown oil; 48% yield; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.91 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.42 (2H, d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.37 (2H, d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.26 (2H, d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 7.19 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 7.11 (2H, d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 7.03 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 6.69 (2H, s, ArH), 5.88 (1H, s, CH), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 141.0, 136.7, 135.5, 128.9, 128.5, 127.1, 123.5, 121.9, 120.0, 119.9, 119.2, 111.0, 39.8, 21.1; MS (ESI) *m/z* 357 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-((4-Methoxyphenyl)methylene)bis(1*H*-indole) (4o)³

Brown solid; 40% yield; mp 188-190 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.89 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.43 (2H, d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.37 (2H, d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.30-7.27 (2H, m, ArH), 7.20 (2H, t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.04 (2H, t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 6.85 (2H, d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, ArH), 6.66 (2H, d, *J* = 1.6 Hz, ArH), 5.87 (1H, s, CH), 3.81 (3H, s, OCH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 157.9, 136.7, 136.2, 129.6, 127.1, 123.5, 121.9, 120.0, 120.0, 119.2, 113.6, 111.0, 55.2, 39.3; MS (ESI) *m/z* 375 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-((4-Fluorophenyl)methylene)bis(1*H*-indole) (4p)¹²

Brown oil; 48% yield; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.92 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.39 (4H, t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.35-7.29 (2H, m, ArH), 7.21 (2H, t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.05 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 6.99 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 6.65 (2H, s, ArH), 5.90 (1H, s, CH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 161.4 (d, *J* = 243.7 Hz), 139.7 (d, *J* = 3.1 Hz), 136.7, 130.0 (d, *J* = 7.9 Hz), 126.9, 123.5, 122.0, 119.8, 119.5, 119.3, 114.9 (d, *J* = 21.2), 111.1, 39.4; ¹⁹F NMR: (376 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: -(117.3-117.42); MS (ESI) *m/z* 425 [M+Na]⁺.

4-(Di(1*H*-indol-3-yl)methyl)phenol (4q)¹³

Brown solid; 41% yield; mp 119-121 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.92 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.44-7.35 (4H, m, ArH), 7.25-7.15 (4H, m, ArH), 7.03 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 6.76 (2H, d, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 6.67 (2H, s, ArH), 5.85 (1H, s, CH), 4.70 (1H, br s, OH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 153.8, 136.7, 136.4, 129.8, 127.0, 123.5, 121.9, 120.0, 120.0, 119.2, 115.0, 111.0, 39.3; MS (ESI) *m/z* 425 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-((2-Bromophenyl)methylene)bis(1*H*-indole) (4r)¹⁴

Pink oil; 88% yield; mp 76-78 °C; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.89 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.65 (1H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.44 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.38 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.27-7.10 (5H, m, ArH), 7.06 (2H, t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, ArH), 6.63 (2H, s, ArH), 6.35 (1H, s, CH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 142.9, 136.7, 132.8, 130.4, 127.8, 127.3, 127.0, 124.8, 123.8, 122.0, 119.9, 119.3, 118.4, 111.1, 39.5; MS (ESI) m/z 423 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3,3'-((2-Chlorophenyl)methylene)bis(1*H*-indole) (4s)¹³

Red oil; 79% yield; mp 76-78 °C; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.91 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.44 (3H, t, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.38 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.27-7.10 (5H, m, ArH), 7.05 (2H, t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, ArH), 6.65 (2H, s, ArH), 6.38 (1H, s, CH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 141.3, 136.7, 134.0, 130.3, 129.5, 127.5, 127.0, 126.6, 123.8, 122.0, 119.8, 119.3, 118.4, 111.0, 36.6; MS (ESI) m/z 379 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3,3'-((Thiophen-2-methylene)bis(1*H*-Indole) (4t)³

Brown solid; 33% yield; mp 181-183 °C; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.93 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.50 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.38 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.24-7.16 (3H, m, ArH), 7.06 (2H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 6.97-6.92 (2H, m, ArH), 6.86 (2H, s, ArH), 6.19 (1H, s, CH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 148.6, 136.6, 126.8, 126.4, 125.1, 123.6, 123.2, 122.0, 119.8, 119.7, 119.4, 111.1, 35.3; MS (ESI) m/z 351 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3,3'-(Oleyl-2-methylene)bis(1*H*-Indole) (4u)¹⁵

Brown oil; 71% yield; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.84 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.65 (2H, d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.35 (2H, d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.20 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 7.09 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 6.99 (2H, s, ArH), 5.49-5.32 (2H, m, 2 x CH=), 4.52 (1H, t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, CH), 2.33-2.19 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.13-1.97 (4H, m, 2 x CH₂), 1.46-1.28 (22H, m, 11 x CH₂), 0.98-0.88 (3H, m, CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 136.6, 129.9, 127.2, 121.7, 121.4, 120.5, 119.6, 118.9, 111.0, 35.8, 34.0, 31.9, 29.8, 29.5, 29.3, 29.3, 28.3, 27.2, 22.7, 14.1; MS (ESI) *m/z* 505 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-(Cyclohexane-1,1-diyl)bis(1*H*-indole) (4v)¹⁶

Brown foam; 25% yield; mp 76-78 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.81 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.65 (2H, d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.32 (2H, d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.15 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 7.05 (2H, s, ArH), 7.00 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 2.66-2.59 (4H, m, 4 x CHH), 1.77-1.64 (6H, m, 6 x CHH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 137.0, 126.2, 123.5, 122.1, 121.4, 121.1, 118.4, 111.1, 39.5, 36.8, 26.7, 23.0; MS (ESI) *m/z* 337 [M+Na]⁺

3,3'-(3-Phenylpropane-1,1-diyl)bis(2-methyl-1*H*-indole) (4w)¹⁷

Green solid; 51% yield; mp 188-190 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.69 (2H, d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.63 (2H, br s, 2 x NH), 7.29 (2H, d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.23 (3H, d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.19 (2H, d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.10 (2H, t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 7.04 (2H, t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, ArH), 4.49 (1H, t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, CH), 2.85-2.72 (4H, m, 2 x CH₂), 2.27 (6H, s, 2 x CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 142.5, 135.1, 130.9, 128.5, 128.4, 128.2, 125.6, 120.4, 119.3, 119.0, 114.5, 110.1, 36.2, 34.9, 34.3, 12.6; MS (ESI) *m/z* 401 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-(3-Phenylpropane-1,1-diyl)bis(1-methyl-1*H*-indole) (4x)¹⁸

Brown oil; 90% yield; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 7.61 (2H, d, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.31 (4H, t, *J* = 7.9 Hz, ArH), 7.26-7.19 (5H, m, ArH), 7.08 (2H, t, *J* = 7.5 Hz, ArH), 6.92 (2H, s, ArH), 4.54 (1H, t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, CH), 3.76 (6H, s, 2 x NCH₃), 2.82-2.73 (2H, m, CH₂), 2.63-2.53 (2H, m, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 142.7, 137.3, 128.5, 128.2, 127.5, 126.3, 125.6, 121.3, 119.7, 118.8, 118.5, 109.1, 37.9, 34.5, 33.3, 32.6; MS (ESI) *m/z* 401 [M+Na]⁺.

3,3'-(3-Phenylpropane-1,1-diyl)bis(1-butyl-1*H*-indole) (4y)¹⁵

Brown oil; 93% yield; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.58 (2H, d, $J = 7.9$ Hz, ArH), 7.35-7.28 (4H, m, ArH), 7.24-7.17 (5H, m, ArH), 7.04 (2H, t, $J = 7.9$ Hz, ArH), 6.97 (2H, s, ArH), 4.53 (1H, t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, CH), 4.10 (4H, t, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 2 x NCH_2), 2.79-2.71 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.64-2.54 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.89-1.76 (4H, m, 2 x CH_2), 1.42-1.30 (4H, m, 2 x CH_2), 0.96 (6H, t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, 2 x CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 142.8, 136.6, 128.5, 128.2, 127.6, 125.6, 125.4, 121.0, 119.9, 118.5, 118.3, 109.3, 45.9, 37.7, 34.5, 33.6, 32.3, 20.2, 13.7; MS (ESI) m/z 485 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3,3'-(3-Phenylpropane-1,1-diyl)bis(1-cyclopentyl-1H-indole) (4z)¹⁵

Green oil; 60% yield; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.60 (2H, d, $J = 7.9$ Hz, ArH), 7.41 (2H, d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, ArH), 7.32 (2H, t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, ArH), 7.26-7.18 (5H, m, ArH), 7.10 (2H, s, ArH), 7.06 (2H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 4.85-4.76 (2H, m, 2 x NCH), 4.54 (1H, t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, CH), 2.78-2.71 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.65-2.57 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.27-2.18 (4H, m, 2 x CH_2), 2.03-1.86 (8H, m, 4 x CH_2), 1.83-1.76 (4H, m, 2 x CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 142.8, 136.8, 128.6, 128.2, 127.7, 125.6, 122.0, 120.9, 119.8, 118.5, 118.3, 109.7, 56.8, 37.7, 34.5, 33.9, 32.5, 24.1, 24.0; MS (ESI) m/z 509 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3,3'-(3-Phenylpropane-1,1-diyl)bis(1-benzyl-1H-indole) (4aa)¹⁵

Brown oil; 96% yield; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.76-7.66 (2H, m, ArH), 7.44-7.32 (10H, m, ArH), 7.32-7.22 (5H, m, ArH), 7.21-7.11 (8H, m, ArH), 5.36 (4H, s, 2 x NCH_2), 4.74-4.61 (1H, m, CH), 2.95-2.81 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.78-2.65 (2H, m, CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 142.6, 137.9, 137.0, 128.7, 128.6, 128.5, 128.2, 127.7, 127.4, 126.5, 125.8, 125.6, 121.5, 119.9, 119.2, 118.7, 109.6, 49.7, 37.4, 34.4, 33.6; MS (ESI) m/z 553 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3,3'-(3-Phenylpropane-1,1-diyl)bis(1-methyl-2-phenyl-1H-indole) (4ab)¹⁹

Brown oil; 59% yield; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.69 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.44-7.35 (4H, m, ArH), 7.34-7.25 (7H, m, ArH), 7.24-7.17 (3H, m, ArH), 7.08 (2H, t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 7.02-6.91 (5H, m, ArH), 4.56 (1H, t, $J = 7.4$ Hz, CH), 3.50 (6H, s, 2 x NCH_3), 2.72-2.59 (4H, m, 2 x CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 142.4, 138.1, 136.9, 132.5, 130.9, 128.4, 128.0, 127.9, 127.6, 127.3, 125.2, 121.0, 120.8, 118.9, 115.8, 109.0, 36.7, 34.4, 34.2, 30.5; MS (ESI) m/z 553 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

3-(1-(1H-Indol-3-yl)-3-phenylpropyl)-1-methyl-1H-indole (4ac)

Colorless oil; 32% yield; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 7.91 (1H, br s, NH), 7.60 (2H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.37 (1H, d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, ArH), 7.34-7.27 (4H, m, ArH), 7.24-7.19 (4H, m, ArH), 7.11-7.04 (3H, m, ArH), 6.90 (1H, s, ArH), 4.55 (1H, t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, CH), 3.75 (3H, s, NCH_3), 2.81-2.73 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.65-2.54 (2H, m, CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 142.7, 137.3, 136.6, 128.5, 128.2, 127.5, 127.1,

126.3, 125.6, 121.8, 121.4, 121.3, 120.2, 119.7, 119.1, 118.6, 118.5, 111.0, 109.1, 37.6, 34.5, 33.4, 32.6; HRMS exact mass calculated for $[M+Na]^+$ ($C_{26}H_{24}N_2Na^+$) requires m/z 387.1832, found m/z 387.1832.

3-(1-(1*H*-Indol-3-yl)-3-phenylpropyl)-1-butyl-1*H*-indole (4ad)

Colorless oil; 13% yield; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 7.80 (1H, br s, NH), 7.71-7.64 (2H, m, ArH), 7.44-7.35 (4H, m, ArH), 7.32-7.23 (5H, m, ArH), 7.18-7.10 (2H, m, ArH), 7.03 (2H, s, ArH), 4.61 (1H, t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, CH), 4.19-4.08 (2H, m, NCH_2), 2.88-2.79 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.72-2.63 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.92-1.82 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.46-1.35 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.02 (3H, t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, CH_3); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 142.7, 136.6, 136.6, 128.5, 128.2, 127.5, 127.0, 125.6, 125.3, 121.6, 121.5, 121.1, 120.1, 119.8, 119.6, 118.9, 118.3, 118.2, 111.0, 109.3, 45.9, 37.5, 34.4, 33.5, 32.3, 20.1, 13.7; HRMS exact mass calculated for $[M+Na]^+$ ($C_{29}H_{30}N_2Na^+$) requires m/z 429.2301, found m/z 429.2289.

5-Bromo-3-(1-(1-methyl-1*H*-indol-3-yl)-3-phenylpropyl)-1*H*-indole (4ae)

Colorless oil; 18% yield; 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 7.91 (1H, br s, NH), 7.70 (1H, s, ArH), 7.55 (1H, d, $J = 7.5$ Hz, ArH), 7.37-7.19 (9H, m, ArH), 7.10-7.03 (2H, m, ArH), 6.91 (1H, s, ArH), 4.46 (1H, t, $J = 7.1$ Hz, CH), 3.77 (3H, s, NCH_3), 2.79-2.72 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.65-2.49 (2H, m, CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 142.4,

137.4, 135.2, 128.8, 128.5, 128.3, 127.3, 126.2, 125.8, 124.7, 122.7, 122.1, 121.4, 120.0, 119.6, 118.5, 118.0, 112.5, 112.4, 109.2, 37.4, 34.4, 33.2, 32.7; HRMS exact mass calculated for $[M+Na]^+$ ($C_{26}H_{23}BrN_2Na^+$) requires m/z 465.0937, found m/z 465.0936.

3,3'-(3-Phenylpropane-1,1-diyl)bis(1*H*-pyrrole) (4af)¹⁹

Brown oil; 45% yield; 1H NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 7.33-7.13 (9H, m, ArH), 5.96 (2H, s, ArH), 3.89-3.80 (1H, m, CH), 2.66-2.57 (2H, m, CH_2), 2.22-2.13 (2H, m, CH_2); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 141.9, 132.7, 128.6, 128.5, 128.5, 128.3, 125.8, 117.7, 108.2, 105.5, 105.4, 105.2, 36.8, 35.2, 33.5; MS (ESI) m/z 273 $[M+Na]^+$.

Recyclability of Graphene Acid

Further studies were performed for the recovery and reuse of GA (Figure S4). After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was diluted in methanol and subsequently, the reaction mixture was filtered through a Nylon membrane filter (0.20 μm), in order to recover GA, which was washed extensively with methanol and dichloromethane, until all the organic residuals were completely removed. The catalyst was recovered, dried and used in the recycling reaction for five times.

Figure S4. Reuse of GA in the synthesis of **4a** (in water HPLC).

Table S11. Elemental composition of GA and recovered GA after the reaction, as obtained from the XPS analyses (integral values of HR-XPS spectra with subtracted Shirley background).

	Atomic percentage [%]			
	C 1s (283 eV)	N 1s (400 eV)	O 1s (531 eV)	F 1s (686 eV)
GA	76.8	3.0	20.2	<1.0
Recovered GA	81.3	5.8	12.9	<1.0

Figure S5. Reuse of GA in the synthesis of **4b** (in tap water).

Figure S6. Survey XPS spectrum of recovered GA after the first cycle reaction in tap water.

Calculation of Specific Productivity

Equation S1: Equation for calculation of specific productivity for heterogeneous catalyst.

$$\text{Specific productivity} = \frac{\text{BIM product (mmol)}}{\text{total catalyst amount (g)} \times \text{reaction time (h)}}$$

Table S12: Confrontation of specific productivity.

Product		 (4t)						
Specific productivity <i>mmol g⁻¹ h⁻¹</i>	GO (Ref 20)	1.02	0.77	0.77	0.48	1.03	0.60	0.60
	GA (This work)	2.87	3.00	2.92	2.00	2.00	1.71	1.77

High Resolution Mass Spectrometry Studies

Instrumentation

The High Resolution Mass Spectra were recorded with a Q-TOF (Time of Flight Mass Spectrometry) Bruker Maxis Impact with the ESI source and U-HPLC Thermo Dionex Ultimate 3000 pump and autosampler. N₂ was used as the collision gas and electrospray ionization (ESI) – positive and negative mode - was used for the MS experiments. The data acquisition was carried out with Data Analysis from Bruker Daltonics (version 4.1). Acetonitrile LC-MS gradient was obtained from Carlo Erba Reagents (Chaussée du Vexin, France). (Source conditions: End plate offset 500V, Capillary 4500V, Nebulizer 0.4 Bar, Dry gas 4.0 l/min, Dry temperature 180 °C and Quadrupole conditions: Ion energy 5 eV, Collision energy 10 eV, Transfer time 143 μs, Collision ion RF 3500 vpp, Pre pulse storage 1 μs). HRMS studies were performed with an ESI source in positive- and negative-ionization mode. The annotation of the intermediates was based on the exact mass high accuracy (mass error lower than 5 ppm) and on the isotopic distribution similarity (mSigma values lower than 50).

Mechanistic studies on the GA-catalysed Friedel-Crafts arylation of indoles with aldehydes

Positive ESI mode

In a glass vial containing graphene acid **3** (2 mg) in Et₂O (1.2 mL), 3-phenyl-propanal (**1a**) (13 mg, 0.10 mmol) and indole (**2a**) (29 mg, 0.25 mmol) were added consecutively. The reaction mixture was stirred at 40 °C. At the specific time of study, a sample of the reaction mixture (20 μL) was first diluted with 980 μL ACN and 100 μL of that sample were further diluted with 900 μL of ACN. Finally, 100 μL were injected for DI-HRMS analysis.

In **Figure S7**, the full scan High Resolution Mass spectra of the reaction mixture at reaction times: A) 0 min, B) 30 min, C) 1 h, D) 2 h, E) 3 h and F) 4 h are presented in positive mode.

A. 0 min

B. 30 min

C. 1 h

D. 2 h

E. 3 h

F. 4 h

Figure S7. Full scan High Resolution Mass spectra of the reaction mixture at reaction times: A) 0 min, B) 30 min, C) 1 h, D) 2 h, E) 3 h and F) 4 h, in positive mode.

In **Figure S8**, the High Resolution Mass spectra of selected intermediates are presented in positive mode.

Chemical Formula: $C_9H_{10}NaO^+$

Exact Mass: 157,0624

Chemical Formula: $C_{17}H_{17}NNaO^+$

Exact Mass: 274,1202

Meas. m/z	#	Ion Formula	m/z	err [ppm]	mSigma	# mSigma	Score	e? Conf	N-Rule
274.1202	1	$C_{17}H_{17}NNaO$	274.1202	0.2	18.9	1	100.00	even	ok

Chemical Formula: $C_{17}H_{16}N^+$

Exact Mass: 234,1277

Meas. m/z	#	Ion Formula	m/z	err [ppm]	mSigma	# mSigma	Score	e? Conf	N-Rule
234.1279	1	$C_{17}H_{16}N$	234.1277	-0.7	47.1	1	100.00	even	ok

Chemical Formula: $C_{25}H_{22}N_2Na^+$

Exact Mass: 373,1675

Figure S8. High Resolution Mass spectra of selected intermediates in positive mode.

Negative ESI mode

In **Figure S9**, the full scan High Resolution Mass spectra of the reaction mixture at reaction times: A) 0 min, B) 30 min, C) 1 h, D) 2 h, E) 3 h and F) 4 h are presented in negative mode.

A. 0 min

B. 30 min

C. 1 h

D. 2 h

E. 3 h

F. 4 h

Figure S9. Full scan High Resolution Mass spectra of the reaction mixture at reaction times: A) 0 min, B) 30 min, C) 1 h, D) 2 h, E) 3 h and F) 4 h, in negative mode.

In **Figure S10**, the High Resolution Mass spectra of selected intermediates are presented in negative mode.

Chemical Formula: $C_8H_6N^-$

Exact Mass: 116,0506

Figure S10. High Resolution Mass spectra of selected intermediates in negative mode.

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4a

4c

4h

4x

